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A record of Partial albinism in Jungle Babbler (*Turdoidea striata*)

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Albinism in birds is a unique phenomenon therefore it has been recorded in several species by various others (Avizanda et al 2010, Dudgeon, 1904; Gurusami, 1992; Inglis, 1903; Javed, 1992; Mahabal, 1993; Prasad, 2000; Pande et al 2005; Pawashe et al 2006; and Sathiyaselvam, 2003; Gupte 1969; Sharma 2003). According to geneticists Hutt and Mueller in 1941, defined four major degrees of albinism,

- 1). Total albinism: the rarest form, in which all the morphology of birds white with pink eyes,
- 2). Incomplete albinism: in this condition melanin pigment completely absent from (birds) feathers, skin, or eyes, but not from all three.
- 3). Imperfect albinism: in which melanin pigment only partially inhibited, creating a pale organism.
- 4). Partial albinism, the most common form, in this condition localized body parts are white or whitish and their legs, and bill are common as other Jungle babblers (*Turdoidea striata*). The majority of white birds are found in this fourth category. Albinism is a condition when the amount of melanin pigments reduces from the body.

Partially albinism or leucism, could result in case of typical white patches in normally darker plumaged birds which are termed as pied. The latter term originated in the literature on domestic poultry and does not appear to have unique scientific meaning.

After around 40 minutes it took to the air with other flocks and start feeding at another nearest side. Thereafter, it separated from the flocks with one common *Jungle babbler* and perched on a tree, and start allo-grooming with other, and this process lasted for 10 minutes, then they perched one twig to another and started locomotion as their behavior, and flew to a dense shrub which away from our site.

Finally with the help of recorded data we came to a conclusion that it is a Partial albino Jungle babbler (*Turdoidea striata*).

Study area:

National Zoological Park (28.6044359°N 77.2461981°E) established in the year 1959. It situated in the middle of a

burgeoning urban Delhi, with an area of 176-acre (71 ha), a sprawling green island and a motley collection of animals and birds. The Zoo area nestled with artificial ponds, good floral, and foraging faunal diversity. The entire area is crisscrossed with a good network of concrete roads.

Observed characteristic

On 5th August 2020 at 2:30 PM, during routine field survey near the Beat No. 14 at National zoological park, Delhi. Author recorded Partial Albino Jungle Babbler (*Turdoidea striata*) among 5 jungle babblers at their feeding time.

Their morphology was similar to other jungle babblers, however, their coloration are totally different. All the feathers on its body was completely white except their primary feather, few patch on tertials and under parts of tail were found black. The beak light pink, tarsus and toes were white in colour. Their size and vocal sound (harsh nasal calls) was similar to other jungle babblers.

All the pictorial and video graphical data was collected with Nikon D3300 with 70-300mm telephoto zoom lens. Albinism had been reported in *Jungle Babbler* earlier by (Sani.T and Kasambe.R.2005). However, Partial albinism had not been reported yet in Jungle Babblers. The report here is with photographic evidence.

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Breeding activities of Yellow-footed Green Pigeon (*Treron phoenicoptera*)

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The Yellow-footed Green Pigeon (*Treron phoenicoptera*) is a resident species found throughout India, which affects dry and moist deciduous forest with a scattering of ficus and other fruiting trees. It also inhabits open country side, around villages and cultivation and even in town and cities. The breeding occurs from March to June occasionally a month or two earlier or later. Nest is a flimsy platform of inter laced twigs in a moderate sized tree, concealed among the foliage normally found on out skirt of forest, near villages and in

gardens. Normally two white coloured elliptical and glossy eggs are laid. (Ali & Ripley 1987, Grimmett *et.al.* 1998)

Akhilesh on 29 03 2019, during a morning safari drive in Kanha Tiger Reserve (KTR), district Balaghat, Madhya Pradesh, Kanha Range observed on the earthen bank of a tank a flock of 10-12 Yellow-footed Green Pigeons (Fig.1,2). the birds were not drinking water but were on the soil possibly picking soil, which they occasionally do descending to

